

Genetic Variants and Atherosclerosis

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Abstract—Atherosclerosis is the condition in which an artery wall thickens as the result of a build-up of fatty materials such as cholesterol. It is a syndrome affecting arterial blood vessels, a chronic inflammatory response in the walls of arteries, in large part due to the accumulation of macrophage white blood cells and promoted by low density (especially small particle) lipoproteins (plasma proteins that carry cholesterol and triglycerides) without adequate removal of fats and cholesterol from the macrophages by functional high density lipoproteins (HDL). It is commonly referred to as a hardening or furring of the arteries. It is caused by the formation of multiple plaques within the arteries.

Keywords—Arterial blood vessels, atherosclerosis, cholesterol.

I. INTRODUCTION

CORONARY artery disease (CAD), or narrowing of the coronary arteries due to atherosclerosis, remains one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Atherosclerosis is the condition in which an artery wall thickens as the result of a build-up of fatty materials such as cholesterol (Figure 1). It is a syndrome affecting arterial blood vessels, a chronic inflammatory response in the walls of arteries, in large part due to the accumulation of macrophage white blood cells and promoted by low density (especially small particle) lipoproteins without adequate removal of fats and cholesterol from the macrophages by functional high density lipoproteins (HDL). It is commonly referred to as a hardening or furring of the arteries. It is caused by the formation of multiple plaques within the arteries [1]. Atherosclerosis is the main cause of CV disease, including ischemic stroke, CHD, and ACS [2-10]. The clinical course related to atherosclerotic changes may not be a gradual and progressive one; rather, patients may remain asymptomatic for years, with sudden death marking the first clinical manifestation [3]. Equally unpredictable is the onset of CV events, which have not correlated well with the commonly used Framingham risk status model. The majority of events are seen in patients categorized as low or intermediate risk of

CHD based on the Framingham risk equation [3]. These data highlight the need for early diagnosis and treatment of subclinical disease. Advances in recent research have provided greater understanding of the underlying pathophysiology of atherosclerosis. Evidence now supports that atherosclerosis is a progressive, dynamic, inflammatory process, which can indeed be modified by preventive and therapeutic measures [7,8,11].

A. Molecular Mechanisms Involved in Formation of Atherosclerotic Plaque

The atherosclerotic plaque or atheroma is the key feature in the development of atherosclerosis. Formation of atheroma lasts over decades, starting with early lesions which may occur in early adolescence. The velocity of progression depends on many factors, such as gender, genetics and some well recognized risk factors (e.g. hyperlipoproteinemia as mentioned below). Once initiated, the atheroma may remain stable for many years, causing only rarely symptoms such as stable angina pectoris or claudicatio. But some factors may lead to an unstable plaque, resulting in more grave or even fatal acute events such as myocardial infarction. In the initiation of atherosclerotic lesions, migration of mononuclear leukocytes is one key feature. This migration is mediated by several cytokines which are produced by the endothelial cells under certain influences [12]. Selectins are one family of those endothelial leukocyte adhesion molecules. One member of this family, namely P selectin, is thought to mediate rolling or transitory contact of leukocytes with the endothelium. It is found to be expressed in endothelial cells overlying human atheromas, but not in those of normal vessels [13]. Another important cytokine involved in leukocyte adhesion and immigration is vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM-1). VCAM-1 is found to be expressed early at sites of atherosclerotic lesion formation in animal models [14]. After adhesion, leukocytes migrate into the artery wall directed by various chemoattractant chemokines. In experimental animals, macrophage chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1) seems to play an important role in this process [15]. Oxidized phospholipids are present in modified lipoproteins such as oxidized LDL and are a link between hyperlipidemia and local increase of adhesion molecules or cytokine expressions at sites of atherosclerotic lesions. Experimental data suggest that those modified phospholipids like lysophosphatidyl choline or palmitoyl oxovaleroylglycerophosphoryl choline are able to trigger expression of adhesion molecules and cytokines involved in plaque formation [16]. After the migration of leukocytes into the intima, they accumulate modified lipids and were transformed to foam cells. The receptor responsible

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for uptake of lipids is named scavenger receptor [17]. The production of mediators like platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF) [18], heparin-binding epidermal growth factor [19] and insulin-like growth factors by endothelial cells and by the mononuclear macrophages themselves mediate the accumulation of smooth muscle cells and of extracellular matrix macromolecules [20]. This process results in formation and growing of progressive atheroma. The stability of such a plaque is due to the composition and thickness of its fibrinous cap. The majority of acute coronary event result from a rupture of this protective cap. The most important factor contributing to the biomechanical strength of this cap are the interstitial forms of collagen. Main collagen production is made by the smooth muscle cells under influence of certain factors such as PDGF. Other factors like interferon gamma inhibit gene expression and protein synthesis in those cells [21]. Gamma interferon is produced by stimulated T cells, which are frequently found accumulating at sites of acute plaque rupture and thrombosis [22]. So the inhibition of collagen synthesis by mediators produced by activated T cells seems to be one key factor in transforming stable plaques to unstable ones. In addition, enzymes of the matrix metalloproteinase family (MMP) produced by activated macrophages may play an important role with proteolytic degradation of formerly produced collagen fibrils [23].

Fig. 1 Micrograph of an artery that supplies the heart with significant atherosclerosis and marked luminal narrowing. Masson's trichrome

B. Types of Plaque

The major constituents of atherosclerotic lesions are matrix proteins (including collagens, proteoglycans, elastin, etc), smooth muscle cells, macrophages and lipids [24]. However, the relative proportions of these components vary among different plaques. At one end of the spectrum are plaques rich in lipids and macrophages, which are commonly referred to as lipid rich plaques [25,26]. At the other end of the spectrum are plaques rich in matrix proteins and smooth muscle cells, which are referred to as fibrotic plaques [25,26]. Lipid rich plaques are prone to rupture, causing myocardial infarction. In comparison, fibrotic plaques are usually more stable but bulkier [25,26]. Although a patient may have more than one

atherosclerotic plaque, an autopsy study of individuals with coronary artery disease showed that in 15% of the subjects all plaques were the fibrotic type, in 13% of the subjects all plaques were of the lipid rich type, and in the remaining subjects both types of plaque were present [27].

C. Physiologic Factors that Increase Risk

Risk factors that cause formation of plaque and increase occurrence of atherosclerosis are: Modifiable factors (eg. Diabetes, dyslipoproteinemia, an LDL:HDL ratio greater than 3:1, elevated serum C-reactive protein concentrations and etc), nonmodifiable factors (eg. Advanced age, male sex, genetic abnormalities and having close relatives who have had some complication of atherosclerosis), lesser or uncertain factors (eg. Being obese, postmenopausal estrogen deficiency, intake of trans fat, Chlamydia pneumoniae infection etc) and dietary risk factors [28].

II. GENETIC VARIANTS RELATED TO ATHEROSCLEROSIS

Although the plaque develops as a chronic inflammatory reaction, there is increasing evidence that DNA damage to cells within the lesion plays an important role in both atherogenesis and the behaviour of established lesions [29-31]. DNA damage ranges from 'macro' damage, including deletions or additions of whole chromosomes or parts of chromosomes, to 'micro' damage, which includes DNA strand breaks, mutations of single bases, modified bases (including oxidation) or DNA adducts. Several genetic variants have been examined in relation to atherosclerosis, more commonly by association than linkage analysis. Findings from the most widely studied variants are summarized, followed by a listing of variants only beginning to be explored in relation to atherosclerosis disease.

A. Matrix Metalloproteinase

The matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), are a family of enzymes required for degradation of the extracellular matrix during embryo development, morphogenesis and tissue remodeling. MMPs degrade most of the extracellular matrix constituents within atherosclerotic plaques [32]. It is well accepted that MMPs are key players in most vascular diseases and a similar elucidation of the spectrum of expression and specific roles has to be effected before a therapeutic opportunity can be clearly identified [33-35]. MMPs have been implicated in intimal thickening, a repair response to damage of the walls of large arteries in human atherosclerotic pathologies, as well as in the subsequent plaque rupture. Hence, the concept of 'good' and 'bad' MMPs can be invoked in cardiovascular disease as in cancer, but the existing data from animal model studies are not clear cut. Studies using MMP gene knockout mice have indicated that MMP-2 and MMP-9 play key roles in cardiac rupture after myocardial infarction [36-42]. A recent study showed that MT1-MMP (MMP-14) is increased after ischemia-reperfusion [43]. TIMP-3 deficiency in mice disrupted matrix homeostasis and caused spontaneous left ventricular dilation, cardiomyocyte hypertrophy and contractile dysfunction [44].

A critical role of MMP-2 and MMP-9 has been also shown for the development of abdominal aortic aneurysm using MMP gene deletion mice [45]. Recent studies on atherosclerotic plaque stability using a series of apoE/MMP double knockout mice have indicated that MMP-3 and MMP-9 have protective roles by limiting plaque growth and enhancing plaque stability, but MMP-12 promotes lesion expansion and destabilization [46]. Chase and Newby [47] have proposed that multiple steps of MMP gene induction occur in vascular pathologies due to the progressive recruitment of different cell types and inductive factors during different phases of the disease. A widening spectrum of MMPs, starting with MMP-2 and MMP-9, leading to MMP-1, MMP-12 and MMP-14, followed by MMP-3, MMP-11 and MMP-13 ultimately leads to a transition from matrix turnover to matrix destruction. An association between the MMP3 5A/6A promoter polymorphism and atherosclerosis was first described in 1995: the 6A/6A genotype was associated with greater progression of coronary atherosclerosis [48]. Functional studies showed that the 6A allele was associated with twofold lower transcriptional activity [49]. Several investigators have used the clinical end point of coronary atherosclerosis or its progression, and >6000 people have been included in such analyses. The 6A/6A genotype was associated with a greater progression of CAD after angioplasty [50]. In a study we examined 190 patients with coronary artery stenosis and 200 controls and indicated that there is a significant association between 6A/6A genotype MMP3 gene polymorphism and Extent of Coronary Atherosclerosis [51].

B. Paraoxonase

The paraoxonase gene family consists of three members of PON1, PON2, and PON3, located adjacent to each other on the long arm of chromosome 7 [52]. All 3 gene products protect low density lipoprotein (LDL) from oxidation, at least in vitro [53]. paraoxonase 1 and 3 (PON1 and PON3) associated with the circulating high density lipoprotein (HDL) particles but paraoxonase 2 (PON2) that expressed widely in a number of tissues including the liver, lungs, brain and heart dose not appear to be associated with HDL [54]. PON1 hydrolyzes organophosphates such as paraoxone, carbomates, and nerve gases, therefore it was initially investigated in the field of toxicology [55]. PON1 has been shown to protect LDL against oxidative modification in vitro by preventing accumulation of lipid peroxides [56]. Peroxidation of LDL is recognized to plays central role in atherogenesis [57]; therefore recently PON1 has been implicated in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular disease (CVD). Several studies have suggested that either paraoxonase-1 (PON1) is associated with oxidative stress [58,59]. The oxidative modification of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) is an important element in the development of atherosclerosis [60]. Numerous studies suggest that oxidative modification of LDL in the arterial wall initiates development of foam cell-laden fatty streaks, which are believed to cause atherosclerosis [61]. Recent evidence suggests that high-density lipoprotein (HDL) inhibits oxidation of LDL and thus, may protect against risk of CAD [62]. Paraoxonase-1, an HDL-associate enzyme, has been shown to be responsible for

this antioxidative property of HDL [63]. Paraoxonase-1 is a 44-kD Ca²⁺-dependent enzyme that is associated with apolipoprotein (Apo) A1 and Apo J on HDL [64,65]. The PON1 gene has 2 common polymorphisms in the coding region, which lead to a glutamine→arginine substitution at position 192 and leucine→methionine substitution at position 55. These sites are identical to positions 54 and 191, when alanine is defined as the N-terminal residue. The variants are designated PON1 M/L55 and R/Q192 [66,67]. Only 2 studies examined the PON 2 S311C polymorphism and found no relationship with carotid atherosclerosis [68,69]. Examination of 2 additional promoter polymorphisms, as well as a haplotype comprising polymorphisms at -162/-108/55/192, failed to detect any association with stenosis cases[70]. Of 13 studies considering the PON 1 192 polymorphism separately or jointly with PON 1 55, 10 showed no association with PON 1 192 considered alone [68,69,70,71,72-77], although 1 of these showed IMT to be higher in subjects homozygous for the PON 1 55 L and PON 1 192Q alleles compared with LL/RR and MM/QQ subjects [77], and another showed the PON 1 192RR genotype to be more common than QQ in stenosis cases but only after adjustment for PON activity level [76]. This report was subsequently refuted in an expanded sample from the same authors, who found no association regardless of adjustment for PON activity [70]. An eleventh study showed higher IMT in RR homozygotes than Q allele carriers [78]; the twelfth showed plaque to be more frequent in PON 1 192R carriers with high levels of high-density lipoprotein, but no difference in plaque by genotype in subjects with low levels of high-density lipoprotein [79]. The thirteenth showed the R allele to be more frequent in older persons with moderate versus no atherosclerosis [80]. It has been shown that the PON1 R allozyme is less efficient at retarding the oxidation of LDL than is the Q allozyme because of the decreased hydrolysis of lipid peroxides by he R allozyme [81,82]. This finding may explain why in our study the PON1 R allele has been found to be present at an increased frequency in coronary artery disease (CAD).This finding is accordance to some studies that performed in different population and coronary artery disease; as in 81 stroke patients who were compared with 2553 control subjects, PON1R was shown to be an independent risk factor for stroke [83]. Similarly in a case-control study of 139 CAD patients and 119 control subjects; RR genotype not only defined as an independent risk factor for CAD; but also as a factor that related with the severity of disease [84].

C. Apolipoprotein E

Apolipoprotein E, a key protein in the transport of cholesterol, has been a suspect in regard to the role played by genetic polymorphisms as risk factors for cardiovascular disease due to atherosclerosis, either as a result of variances in cholesterol transport among genotypes or by direct effect of the polymorphisms upon human atherogenesis [85-87]. Apolipoprotein (apo) ε is a member of the apolipoprotein gene family. Other members of this multigene family include apo A-I, apo A-II, apo A-IV, apo C-I, apo C-II, and apo C-III. The coding regions of these genes are composed of tandem repeats of 11 codons, which suggests that they have evolved through

duplications of a primordial gene[88]. While there are rare variants, it is the polymorphism with its three alleles, ϵ_2 , ϵ_3 , and ϵ_4 , that has been studied in relation to cardiovascular disease. From these alleles arise six phenotypes; their ranking from most to least common is generally 3/3, 4/3, 3/2, 4/4, 4/2, and 2/2 [89]. Apo E helps to stabilize and solubilize lipoproteins as they circulate in the blood. In general, the role of apolipoproteins in lipid metabolism includes maintaining the structural integrity of lipoproteins, serving as cofactors in enzymatic reactions, and acting as ligands for lipoprotein receptors. Apo E is critical in the formation of very low density lipoprotein (VLDL) and chylomicrons. compared with carriers of the ϵ_3 or ϵ_4 allele, carriers of the ϵ_2 allele are slower to clear dietary fat from their blood [90]. The difference in uptake of postprandial lipoprotein particles results in differences in regulating hepatic low density lipoprotein (LDL) receptors, which in turn contributes to genotypic differences in total and LDL cholesterol levels [89,91-95]. High levels of LDL cholesterol have been associated with increased risk of coronary heart disease (CHD). Sing and Davignon demonstrated that 8.3 percent of the total variance for LDL cholesterol is accounted for by the apo ϵ gene locus [96]. Apo ϵ contributes more to normal cholesterol variability than any other gene identified thus far in cholesterol metabolism [96]. In a population-based study Venkutaramana et al [97] reported that the allele frequencies in Indian population 85%-92% for ϵ_3 allele, 3.9% for ϵ_4 allele and 3.5% for ϵ_2 allele. In a study [98] we indicated that Apo ϵ allele frequencies in the control group of Tehran population are 34%, 34% and 32% for ϵ_4 , ϵ_3 and ϵ_2 respectively which are not comparable with the study of Venkutaramana et al and others [97]. The reasons for these discrepancies could be genetic heterogeneity and gene environment interactions in different ethnic population. It is well known that the ϵ_4 allele of Apo E is associated with increased prevalence of atherosclerosis and cardiac heart disease (CHD) [99,100]. However there are controversial results concerning the association between Apo E genotypes and some cardiovascular risk factors. Some studies have suggested that high blood pressure may be associated with the presence of the ϵ_4 allele [101-103], while others have found its association with ϵ_2 allele [104]. However no association was found in few studies [104]. In our study we evaluated the distribution of Apo E genotype and alleles in angiographically defined CAD patients and control subjects, and found these polymorphisms as risk factors for atherosclerosis [98].

D. Renin-angiotensin System

The renin-angiotensin system, a two-enzyme cascade, plays an important role in the regulation of blood pressure, fluid balance, and electrolyte homeostasis [105,106] and in the pathogenesis of cardiovascular disease [107,108]. The initial enzyme, renin, cleaves its substrate, angiotensinogen, to angiotensin I, a decapeptide. Angiotensin I undergoes a second cleavage, mainly by tissue-bound angiotensin-converting enzyme and serine proteinase [109], to generate angiotensin II (an octapeptide), which via the angiotensin II type 1 receptor acts as a potent vasoconstrictor and aldosterone stimulating peptide. The angiotensin-converting

enzyme also inactivates the nonapeptide bradykinin and blocks the tissue kallikrein system. Inhibition of the angiotensin-converting enzyme and antagonism of the angiotensin II type 1 receptor decrease blood pressure in hypertensive patients [110,111], and more importantly also prevent mortality and morbidity in patients with symptomatic or asymptomatic congestive heart failure [112-114], acute myocardial infarction [115], or diabetic nephropathy [116]. Cloning of the human genes coding for the angiotensin-converting enzyme [117,118], angiotensinogen [119], and the angiotensin II type 1 receptor [120] has led to the discovery of several polymorphisms, which may play a role as risk factors for cardiovascular disorders, such as hypertension, coronary heart disease, or cardiomyopathy. Among these genetic mutations, the angiotensin-converting enzyme gene deletion/insertion (D/I) [121], angiotensinogen gene M235T [122], and the angiotensin II type 1 receptor gene A1166C [120] polymorphisms have been extensively investigated in various populations with a variety of cardiovascular disorders. Several other polymorphisms, in particular in the promoter region of the angiotensinogen gene, were also found to be associated with cardiovascular disease [123-127].

1. D/I polymorphism of the angiotensin-converting enzyme gene

In a landmark study, Cambien et al [128] observed an increased prevalence of the angiotensin-converting enzyme DD genotype in 610 Caucasian patients with a history of myocardial infarction. Subsequent studies found that the D allele was also associated with a higher risk of coronary heart disease [129,130], stroke [131,132], other atherosclerotic manifestations [133], or having a history of coronary heart disease [134,135]. One quantitative overview [121] demonstrated a strong association between atherosclerotic cardiovascular complications and the D/I polymorphism of the angiotensin-converting enzyme gene.

2. M235T angiotensinogen gene polymorphism

Several studies [136-138] demonstrated a significant association between coronary heart disease and the M235T polymorphism. However, in 12 studies combined, the T allele was not associated with atherosclerotic cardiovascular complications [122]. The pooled excess risk of 17% (P=0.08) in TT vs. MM homozygotes did not exceed the threshold of statistical significance in nine reports on coronary heart disease, including myocardial infarction. Similarly, for stroke and various other atherosclerotic manifestations, such as restenosis after angioplasty or the presence of atherosclerotic lesions [139,140], there was no excess risk in TT homozygotes compared with MM homozygotes.

3. A1166C polymorphism of the angiotensin II type 1 receptor gene

At least three studies observed synergistic effects of the angiotensin-converting enzyme D/I and the angiotensin II type 1 receptor A1166C polymorphisms on the risk of myocardial infarction [141] or coronary heart disease [142-143]. In a case-control study of 613 myocardial infarction cases and 723

age-matched population controls [141], the odds ratio associated with the angiotensin-converting enzyme DD genotype was 1.05 (95% CI 0.75–1.49) in subjects without the C allele of the angiotensin II type 1 receptor gene, 1.52 (95% CI 1.06–2.18) in AC heterozygotes and 3.95 (95% CI 1.26–12.4) in CC homozygotes (test for trend $P < 0.02$).

III. OTHER POLYMORPHISMS

Genetic variants related to hemostatic and inflammatory factors, interleukins and immune response [144–152], platelet receptors [153–160], and oxidative pathways [161–163], have also been studied sporadically. Associations with hemostasis-related variants have generally been absent [164–166] or present only in subgroups [153,167]. The Marburg I variant of factor VII activating protease and factor V Leiden, however, have been shown to be more frequent in those with plaque progression [168], whereas the β -fibrinogen C148T polymorphism in the homozygous TT form was associated with higher plaque score [168], although none of these associations was replicated in a large sample from the Framingham Heart Study [154].

IV. CONCLUSION

There is much to be learned regarding the genetic contribution to the observed phenotypic variability of atherosclerosis. Several questions that require answers include the following: To what extent do polymorphisms in relevant genes account for the observed variability in the phenotypic expression of pathologies that cannot be accounted for by risk factors alone, and what are their frequencies in populations? How do genetic differences alter the response to treatment strategies?

REFERENCES

- [1] Maton, Anthea, Roshan L, et al. Human Biology and Health. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey, USA: Prentice Hall. (1993); ISBN 0-13-981176-1. OCLC 32308337
- [2] Ridker PM. Inflammation, atherosclerosis, and cardiovascular risk: an epidemiologic view. *Blood Coagul Fibrinolysis*. 1999;10(suppl 1):S9-S12.
- [3] Crouse JR, Grobbee DE, O'Leary DH, et al. Measuring effects on intima media thickness: an evaluation of rosuvastatin in subclinical atherosclerosis—the rationale and methodology of the METEOR study. *Cardiovasc Drugs Ther*. 2004;18:231-238.
- [4] Viles-Gonzalez JF, Fuster V, Badimon JJ. Atherothrombosis: a widespread disease with unpredictable and life-threatening consequences. *Eur Heart J*. 2004;25: 1197-1207.
- [5] Jensen LO, Thayssen P, Pedersen KE, et al. Regression of coronary atherosclerosis by simvastatin: a serial intravascular ultrasound study. *Circulation*. 2004;110: 265-270.
- [6] Rauch U, Osende JI, Fuster V, et al. Thrombus formation on atherosclerotic plaques: pathogenesis and clinical consequences. *Ann Intern Med*. 2001;134:224-238.
- [7] Ohashi R, Mu H, Yao Q, et al. Atherosclerosis: immunopathogenesis and immunotherapy. *Med Sci Monit*. 2004; 10:RA255-RA260.
- [8] Hansson GK. Inflammation, atherosclerosis, and coronary artery disease. *N Engl J Med*. 2005;352: 1685-1695.
- [9] Ben-Haim S, Israel O. PET/CT for atherosclerotic plaque imaging. *QJ Nucl Med Mol Imaging*. 2006;50: 53-60.

- [10] Van Mieghem CAG, McFadden EP, de Feyter PJ, et al. Noninvasive detection of subclinical coronary atherosclerosis coupled with assessment of changes in plaque characteristics using novel invasive imaging modalities. The Integrated Biomarker and Imaging Study. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2006;47:1134-1142.
- [11] Weissberg PL. Atherogenesis: current understanding of the causes of atheroma. *Heart*. 2000;83:247-252.
- [12] Carlos TM, Harlan JM. Leukocyte-endothelial adhesion molecules. *Blood* 1994;84:2068-101.
- [13] Vora DK, Fang ZT, Liva SM, et al. Induction of P-selectin by oxidized lipoproteins. Separate effects on synthesis and surface expression. *Circ Res* 1997;80:810-8.
- [14] Iiyama K, Hajra L, Iiyama M, et al. Patterns of vascular cell adhesion molecule-1 and intercellular adhesion molecule-1 expression in rabbit and mouse atherosclerotic lesions and at sites predisposed to lesion formation. *Circ Res* 1999;85:199-207.
- [15] Gu L, Okada Y, Clinton SK, et al. Absence of monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 reduces atherosclerosis in low density lipoprotein receptor-deficient mice. *Mol Cell* 1998;2:275-81.
- [16] Watson AD, Leitinger N, Navab M, et al. Structural identification by mass spectrometry of oxidized phospholipids in minimally oxidized low density lipoprotein that induce monocyte/endothelial interactions and evidence for their presence in vivo. *J Biol Chem* 1997;272:13597-607.
- [17] von Eckardstein A, Nofer JR, Assmann G. High density lipoproteins and arteriosclerosis. Role of cholesterol efflux and reverse cholesterol transport. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol* 2001; 21:13-27.
- [18] Libby P, Warner SJ, Salomon RN, et al. Production of platelet-derived growth factor-like mitogen by smooth-muscle cells from human atheroma. *N Engl J Med* 1988;318:1493-8.
- [19] Higashiyama S, Abraham JA, Miller J, et al. A heparin-binding growth factor secreted by macrophage-like cells that is related to EGF. *Science* 1991;251:936-9.
- [20] Libby P. Changing concepts of atherogenesis. *J Intern Med* 2000; 247:349-58
- [21] Amento EP, Ehsani N, Palmer H, et al. Cytokines and growth factors positively and negatively regulate interstitial collagen gene expression in human vascular smooth muscle cells. *Arterioscler Thromb* 1991;11:1223-30
- [22] van der Wal AC, Becker AE, van der Loos CM, et al. Site of intimal rupture or erosion of thrombosed coronary atherosclerotic plaques is characterized by an inflammatory process irrespective of the dominant plaque morphology. *Circulation* 1994;89:36-44.
- [23] Galis ZS, Sukhova GK, Lark MW, et al. Increased expression of matrix metalloproteinases and matrix degrading activity in vulnerable regions of human atherosclerotic plaques. *J Clin Invest* 1994;94:2493-503.
- [24] Ross R. The pathogenesis of atherosclerosis: a perspective for the 1990s. *Nature* 1993;362:801-9.
- [25] Libby P. Molecular bases of the acute coronary syndromes. *Circulation* 1995;91:2844-50.
- [26] Davies MJ. Stability and instability: two faces of coronary atherosclerosis. The Paul Dudley White Lecture 1995. *Circulation* 1996; 94:2013-20.
- [27] Hangartner JR, Charleston AJ, Davies MJ, Thomas AC. Morphological characteristics of clinically significant coronary artery stenosis in stable angina. *Br Heart J* 1986;56:501-8.
- [28] Blankenhorn DH, Hodis HN (August 1993). "Atherosclerosis--reversal with therapy". *The Western journal of medicine* 159 (2): 172-9. PMID 8212682.
- [29] Botto N, Rizza A, Colombo M, Mazzone A, Manfredi S, Masetti S, et al. Evidence for DNA damage in patients with coronary artery disease. *Mutat Res* 2001;493:23-30.
- [30] Andreassi MG, Botto N, Cocci F, et al. Methylene tetrahydrofolate reductase gene C677T polymorphism, homocysteine, vitamin B12, and DNA damage in coronary artery disease. *Hum Genet* 2003;112:171-7.
- [31] Botto N, Berti S, Manfredi S, et al. Detection of mtDNA with 4977bp deletion in blood cells and atherosclerotic lesions of patients with coronary artery disease. *Mutat Res* 2005;570:81-8.
- [32] Henney AM, Wakeley PR, Davies MJ, et al. Localization of stromelysin gene expression in atherosclerotic plaques by in situ hybridization. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 1991;88:8154-8.
- [33] Galis, Z.S., Khatri, J.J., 2002. Matrix metalloproteinases in vascular remodeling and atherogenesis: the good, the bad, and the ugly. *Circ. Res.* 90 (3), 251-262.

- [34] Newby, A.C., 2005. Dual role of matrix metalloproteinases (matrixins) in intimal thickening and atherosclerotic plaque rupture. *Physiol Rev.* 85 (1), 1–31.
- [35] Newby, A.C., Johnson, J.L., 2005. Genetic strategies to elucidate the roles of matrix metalloproteinases in atherosclerotic plaque growth and stability. *Circ. Res.* 97 (10), 958–960.
- [36] Hayashidani, S., Tsutsui, H., Ikeuchi, M., et al. Targeted deletion of MMP 2 attenuates early LV rupture and late remodeling after experimental myocardial infarction. 2003; *Am. J. Physiol. Heart Circ. Physiol.* 285 (3), H1229–H1235
- [37] Heymans, S., Lutun, A., Nuyens, D., et al. Inhibition of plasminogen activators or matrix metalloproteinases prevents cardiac rupture but impairs therapeutic angiogenesis and causes cardiac failure. 1999; *Nature Med.* 5 (10), 1135–1142.
- [38] Matsumura, S., Iwanaga, S., Mochizuki, S., Okamoto, H., Ogawa, S., Okada, Y., Targeted deletion or pharmacological inhibition of MMP-2 prevents cardiac rupture after myocardial infarction in mice. 2005a; *J. Clin. Invest.* 115 (3), 599–609.
- [39] Matsumura, S., Iwanaga, S., Mochizuki, S., Okamoto, H., Ogawa, S., Okada, Y., Targeted deletion or pharmacological inhibition of MMP-2 prevents cardiac rupture after myocardial infarction in mice. 2005b; *J. Clin. Invest.* 115 (3), 599–609.
- [40] Romanic, A.M., Harrison, S.M., Bao, W., et al. Myocardial protection from ischemia/reperfusion injury by targeted deletion of matrix metalloproteinase-9. 2002a; *Cardiovasc. Res.* 54 (3), 549–558.
- [41] Romanic, A.M., Harrison, S.M., Bao, W., et al. Myocardial protection from ischemia/reperfusion injury by targeted deletion of matrix metalloproteinase-9. 2002b; *Cardiovasc. Res.* 54 (3), 549–558.
- [42] Romanic, A.M., Harrison, S.M., Bao, W., et al. Myocardial protection from ischemia/reperfusion injury by targeted deletion of matrix metalloproteinase-9. 2002c; *Cardiovasc. Res.* 54 (3), 549–558.
- [43] Deschamps, A.M., Yarbrough, W.M., Squires, C.E., et al. Trafficking of the membrane type-1 matrix metalloproteinase in ischemia and reperfusion: relation to interstitial membrane type-1 matrix metalloproteinase activity. 2005; *Circulation* 111 (9), 1166–1174.
- [44] Fedak, P.W., Smookler, D.S., Kassiri, Z., et al. TIMP-3 deficiency leads to dilated cardiomyopathy. 2004; *Circulation* 110 (16), 2401–2409.
- [45] Longo, G.M., Xiong, W., Greiner, T.C., Zhao, Y., Fiotti, N., Baxter, B.T., Matrix metalloproteinases 2 and 9 work in concert to produce aortic aneurysms. 2002; *J. Clin. Invest.* 110 (5), 625–632.
- [46] Johnson, J.L., George, S.J., Newby, A.C., Jackson, C.L., Divergent effects of matrix metalloproteinases 3, 7, 9, and 12 on atherosclerotic plaque stability in mouse brachiocephalic arteries. 2005; *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 102 (43), 15575–15580.
- [47] Chase, A.J., Newby, A.C., Regulation of matrix metalloproteinase (matrixin) genes in blood vessels: a multi-step recruitment model for pathological remodeling. 2003; *J. Vasc. Res.* 40 (4), 329–343.
- [48] Ye S, Watts GF, Mandalia S, Humphries SE, Henney AM. Preliminary report: genetic variation in the human stromelysin promoter is associated with progression of coronary atherosclerosis. *Br Heart J* 1995;73:209–15.
- [49] Ye S, Eriksson P, Hamsten A, Kurkinen M, Humphries SE, Henney AM. Progression of coronary atherosclerosis is associated with a common genetic variant of the human stromelysin-1 promoter which results in reduced gene expression. *J Biol Chem* 1996;271:13055–60.
- [50] Humphries S, Bauters C, Meirhaeghe A, Luong L, Bertrand M, Amouyel P. The 5A6A polymorphism in the promoter of the stromelysin-1 (MMP3) gene as a risk factor for restenosis. *Eur Heart J* 2002;23:721–5.
- [51] Seifi M, Fallah S, Firoozrai M. Influence of Genetic Polymorphism in Matrix Metalloproteinase-3 on Extent of Coronary Atherosclerosis and Risk of Coronary Artery Stenosis. *Archives Medical Research.* In press
- [52] Primo-Parmo SL, Sorenson RC, Teiber J, La Du BN. The human serum paraoxonase/arylesterase gene (PON1) is one member of a multigene family. *Genomics.* 1996;33:498–507.
- [53] Watson AD, Berliner JA, Hama SY, La Du BN, Faull KF, Fogelman AM, Navab M. Protective effect of high density lipoprotein associated paraoxonase. Inhibition of the biological activity of minimally oxidized low density lipoprotein. *J Clin Invest.* 1995;96:2882–2891.
- [54] Ng CJ, Wadleigh DJ, Gangopadhyay A, Hama S, Grijalva VR, Navab M, Fogelman AM, Reddy ST. Paraonase-2 is a ubiquitously expressed protein with antioxidant properties and is capable of preventing cell-mediated oxidative modification of low density lipoprotein. *J Biol Chem.* 2001;276:44444–44449.
- [55] Li B, Sedlacek M, Manoharan I, Boopathy R, Duysen EG, Masson P, Lockridge O. Butyrylcholinesterase, paraoxonase, and albumin esterase, but not carboxylesterase, are present in human Plasma. *Biochem Pharmacol.* 2005;70: 1673–1684.
- [56] Aviram M, Rosenblat M, Bisgaier CL, Newton RS, Primo-Parmo SL, La Du BN. Paraonase inhibits high-density lipoprotein oxidation and preserves its functions: a possible peroxidative role for paraonase. *J Clin Invest.* 1998;101:1581–1590.
- [57] Durrington P.N, Mackness B and Mackness M.I. Paraonase and atherosclerosis. *Arterioscler.Tromb.Vasc.Biol.*2001;21:473–480
- [58] Kuremoto K, Watanabe Y, Ohmura H et al: R/R genotype of human paraonase (PON1) is more protective against lipoprotein oxidation and coronary artery disease in Japanese subjects. *J Atheroscler Thromb,* 2003; 10: 85–92
- [59] Huang Y, Mironova M, Lopes-Virella MF: Oxidized LDL stimulates matrix metalloproteinase-1 expression in human vascular endothelial cells. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol,* 1999; 19: 2640–47
- [60] Navab M, Berliner JA, Watson AD et al: The yin and yang of oxidation in the development of fatty streak: a review based on the 1994 George Lyman Duff Memorial Lecture. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol,* 1996; 16: 831–42
- [61] Navab M, Hama SY, Anantharamaiah GM et al: Normal high-density lipoprotein inhibits three steps in the formation of mildly oxidized low density lipoprotein: steps 2 and 3. *J Lipid Res,* 2000; 41: 1495–508
- [62] Mackness MI, Durrington PN: HDL, its enzymes and its potential to influence lipid peroxidation. *Atherosclerosis,* 1995; 115: 243–53
- [63] Watson AD, Berliner JA, Hama SY et al: Protective effect of high density lipoprotein associated paraonase: inhibition of biological activity of minimally oxidized low density lipoprotein. *J Clin Invest,* 1995; 96: 2882–91
- [64] Blatter MC, James RW, Messmer S et al: Identification of a distinct human high-density lipoprotein subspecies defined by a lipoprotein-associated protein, K-45: identity of K-45 with paraonase. *Eur J Biochem,* 1993; 211: 871–79
- [65] Kelso GJ, Stuart WD, Richter RJ et al: Apolipoprotein J is associated with paraonase in human plasma. *Biochemistry,* 1994; 33: 832–39
- [66] Humbert R, Adler DA, Disteche CM et al: The molecular basis of the human serum paraonase activity polymorphism. *Nat Genet,* 1993; 3: 73–76
- [67] Adkins S, Gan KN, Mody M, La du DN: Molecular basis for the polymorphic form of human serum paraonase/arylesterase: glutamine or arginine at position 191, for the respective A or B alleles. *Am J Hum Genet,* 1993; 52: 598–60
- [68] Fortunato G, Rubba P, Panico S, Trono D, Tinto N, Mazzaccara C, De Michele M, Iannuzzi A, Vitale DF, Salvatore F, Sacchetti L. A paraonase gene polymorphism, PON 1 (55), as an independent risk factor for increased carotid intima-media thickness in middle-aged women. *Atherosclerosis.* 2003;167:141–148.
- [69] Markus H, Kapozsta Z, Ditrich R, Wolfe C, Ali N, Powell J, Mendell M, Cullinane M. Increased common carotid intima-media thickness in UK African Caribbeans and its relation to chronic inflammation and vascular candidate gene polymorphisms. *Stroke.* 2001;32:2465–2471.
- [70] Jarvik GP, Hatsukami TS, Carlson C, Richter RJ, Jampsa R, Brophy VH, Margolin S, Rieder M, Nickerson D, Schellenberg GD, Heagerty PJ, Furlong CE. Paraonase activity, but not haplotype utilizing the linkage disequilibrium structure, predicts vascular disease. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol.* 2003;1923:1465–1471
- [71] Pallaud C, Sass C, Zannad F, Siest G, Visvikis S. APOC3, CETP, fibrinogen, and MTHFR are genetic determinants of carotid intima-media thickness in healthy men (the Stanislas cohort). *Clin Genet.* 2001;59:316–324.
- [72] Schmidt H, Schmidt R, Niederkorn K, Gradert A, Schumacher M, Watzinger N, Hartung HP, Kostner GM. Paraonase PON1 polymorphism leu-Met54 is associated with carotid atherosclerosis: results of the Austrian Stroke Prevention Study. *Stroke.* 1998;29:2043–2048.
- [73] Koch M, Hering S, Barth C, Ehner M, Enderle MD, Pfohl M. Paraonase1 192 Gln/Arg gene polymorphism and cerebrovascular disease: interaction with type 2 diabetes. *Exp Clin Endocrinol Diabetes.* 2001;109:141–145.
- [74] Cao H, Girard-Globa A, Serusclat A, Bernard S, Bondon P, Picard S, Berthezene F, Moulin P. Lack of association between carotid intima-

- media thickness and paraoxonase gene polymorphism in noninsulin dependent diabetes mellitus. *Atherosclerosis*. 1998;138: 361–366.
- [75] Dessi M, Gnasso A, Motti C, Pujia A, Irace C, Casciani S, Staffa F, Federici G, Cortese C. Influence of the human paraoxonase polymorphism (PON1 192) on the carotid-wall thickening in a healthy population. *Coron Artery Dis*. 1999;10:595–599.
- [76] Jarvik GP, Rozek LS, Brophy VH, Hatsukami TS, Richter RJ, Schellenberg GD, Furlong CE. Paraoxonase (PON1) phenotype is a better predictor of vascular disease than is PON1(192) or PON1(55) genotype. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol*. 2000;20:2441–2447.
- [77] Leus FR, Wittekoek ME, Prins J, Kastelein JJ, Voorbij HA. Paraoxonase gene polymorphisms are associated with carotid arterial wall thickness in subjects with familial hypercholesterolemia. *Atherosclerosis*. 2000; 149:371–377.
- [78] Sakai T, Matsuura B, Onji M. Serum paraoxonase activity and genotype distribution in Japanese patients with diabetes mellitus. *Intern Med*. 1998;37:581–584.
- [79] Gnasso A, Motti C, Irace C, Di G, I, Pujia A, Leto E, Ciamei M, Crivaro A, Bernardini S, Federici G, Cortese C. The Arg allele in position 192 of PON1 is associated with carotid atherosclerosis in subjects with elevated HDLs. *Atherosclerosis*. 2002;164:289–295.
- [80] Zuliani G, Cherubini A, Volpato S, Palmieri E, Mecocci P, De Rango P, Cao P, Costantini F, Mezzetti A, Mascoli F, Senin U, Fellin R. Genetic factors associated with the absence of atherosclerosis in octogenarians. *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci*. 2002;57:M611–M615.
- [81] Mackness MI, Arrol S, Mackness B, Durrington PN. The alloenzymes of paraoxonase determine the effectiveness of high-density lipoprotein in protecting low density lipoprotein against lipid-peroxidation. *Lancet*. 1997;349:851–852.
- [82] Aviram M, Hardk E, Vaya J, Mahmood S, Milo S, Hoffman A, Billicke S, Draganov D, Rosenblat M. Human serum paraoxonase (PON1) Q and R selectively decrease lipid peroxides in human coronary and carotid arteriosclerotic lesions. *Circulation*. 2000; 101: 2510-2517.
- [83] Ranade K, Kirchgessner T.G, Jakubova O.A, Devlin J.J, Delmonte T, Vishnupad P and al. Evaluation of the paraoxonases as candidate genes for stroke: Gln192Arg polymorphism 1 gene is associated with increased risk of stroke. *Stroke*. 2005;36:2346-2350.
- [84] Ozkok E, Aydin M, Babalik E, Ozbek Z, Ince N, Kara I. Combined impact of matrix metalloproteinase-3 and paraoxonase 1 55/192 gene variants on coronary artery disease in Turkish patients. *Med Sci Monit*. 2008; 14(10): 536-542.
- [85] Sing CF, Davignon J. Role of the apolipoprotein E polymorphism in determining normal plasma lipid and lipoprotein variation. *Am J Hum Genet* 1985;37:265–8.
- [86] Davignon J, Gregg RE, Sing CF. Apolipoprotein E polymorphism and atherosclerosis. *Arteriosclerosis* 1988;8:1–21.
- [87] Pathobiological Determinants of Atherosclerosis in Youth (PDAY) Research Group, Hixson JE. Apolipoprotein E polymorphisms affect atherosclerosis in young males. *Arterioscler Thromb* 1991;11:1237–44.
- [88] Luo CC, Li WH, Moore MN, et al. Structure and evolution of the apolipoprotein multigene family. *J Mol Biol* 1986;187:325–40.
- [89] Davignon J, Gregg RE, Sing CF. Apolipoprotein E polymorphism and atherosclerosis. *Arteriosclerosis* 1988;8:1–21.
- [90] Weintraub MS, Eisenberg S, Breslow JL. Dietary fat clearance in normal subjects is regulated by genetic variation in apolipoprotein E. *J Clin Invest* 1987;80:1571–7.
- [91] Hanis CL, Hewett-Emmett D, Douglas TC, et al. Effects of the apolipoprotein E polymorphism on levels of lipids, lipoproteins, and apolipoproteins among Mexican-Americans in Starr County, Texas. *Arterioscler Thromb* 1991;11:362–70.
- [92] Kataoka S, Robbins DC, Cowan LD, et al. Apolipoprotein E polymorphism in American Indians and its relation to plasma lipoproteins and diabetes: the Strong Heart Study. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol* 1996;16:918–25.
- [93] Schaefer EJ, Lamon-Fava S, Johnson S, et al. Effects of gender and menopausal status on the association of apolipoprotein E phenotype with plasma lipoprotein levels: results from the Framingham Offspring Study. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol* 1994;14:1105–13.
- [94] Hallman DM, Boerwinkle E, Saha N, et al. The apolipoprotein E polymorphism: a comparison of allele frequencies and effects in nine populations. *Am J Hum Genet* 1991;49:338–49.
- [95] Lehtinen S, Lehtimäki T, Sisto T, et al. Apolipoprotein E polymorphism, serum lipids, myocardial infarction and severity of angiography verified coronary artery disease in men and women. *Atherosclerosis* 1995;114:83–91.
- [96] Sing CF, Davignon J. Role of the apolipoprotein E polymorphism in determining normal plasma lipid and lipoprotein variation. *Am J Hum Genet* 1985;37:268–85.
- [97] Ventakaramana P, Chengal RE and Ferrell RE. Apolipoprotein E polymorphism in two populations of Andhra Pradesh. *Ind J Hum Genet* 2002; 3: 1-5.
- [98] Fallah S, Seifi M, Firoozrai M, Godarzi T, Jafarzadeh M, Ghohari L.H. Influence of apo E gene polymorphism on Coronary artery disease. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Cellular and Molecular Bioengineering*; 2009 sept 23-25; Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2009
- [99] Uterman G, Hardewig A and Zimmer F. Apolipoprotein E phenotypes in patients with myocardial infarction. *Hum Genet*. 1984; 65: 237-241.
- [100] Lehtinen Lehtimäki T, Sisto, Salenius TP, Mikkilä M and Jakela H. Apolipoprotein E polymorphism, serum lipid, myocardial infarction and severity of angiographically verified coronary artery disease in men and women. *Atherosclerosis*; 1995; 114: 83-91.
- [101] Dembinska Kiee A, Kawecka- Jaszcz K, Kwasiak M, Gaevaro I, Pankiewicz J and Maiczewska Malec M. Apo E isoforms, insulin out put and plasma lipid levels in essential by hypertension. *Eur J Clin Invest*, 1998; 28: 95-99.
- [102] Yilmaz H, Isbir J, Agachan B and Aydin M. Is epsilon 4 allele of apolipoprotein E associated with more severe end stage in essential hypertension? *Cell Biochem. Funct* 2001; 19: 191-195.
- [103] Li X, Duy, DUY and Huang X. Association of apolipoprotein E gene polymorphism with essential hypertension and its complication. *Clin Exp Med*. 2003; 2: 175-179.
- [104] Couderc R, Mahleumof, Bailleu S, Fencon G, Mary R, Fermahken J. Prevalence of apolipoprotein E phenotypes in ischemic cerebrovascular disease. *Stroke* 1993; 24: 661-664.
- [105] Sealey, J.E., James, G.D., Laragh, J.H., 1995. The renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system for normal regulation of blood pressure and sodium and potassium homeostasis. In: Laragh, J.H., Brenner, B.M., Eds., *Hypertension. Pathophysiology, Diagnosis and Management*, vol. 2, Raven Press, New York, NY, USA, pp. 1763–1796
- [106] Hall, J.H., Mizelle, H.L., Woods, L.L., 1986. The renin-angiotensin system and long-term regulation of blood pressure. *J. Hypertens*. 4, 387–397.
- [107] Dzau, V.J., 1993. Tissue renin-angiotensin system in myocardial hypertrophy and failure. *Arch. Intern. Med*. 153, 937–942.
- [108] Campbell, D.J., 1987. Tissue renin-angiotensin system: sites of angiotensin formation. *J. Cardiovasc. Pharmacol*. 10_Suppl. 7., S1–S8.
- [109] Urata, H., Nishimura, H., Ganten, D., 1996. Chymase-dependent angiotensin II forming system in humans. *Am. J. Hypertens*. 9, 277–277.
- [110] MacKay, J.H., Arcuri, K.E., Goldberg, A.I., Snapinn, S.M., Sweet, C.S., 1996. Losartan and low-dose hydrochlorothiazide in patients with essential hypertension. A double-blind placebo-controlled trial of concomitant administration compared with individual components. *Arch. Intern. Med*. 156, 278–285.
- [111] Azizi, M., Guyene, T.T., Chatellier, G., Wargon, M., Me'nard, J., 1997. Additive effects of losartan and enalapril on blood pressure and plasma active renin. *Hypertension* 29, 634–640.
- [112] Sharpe, N., Murphy, J., Smith, H., Hannon, S., 1988. Treatment of patients with symptomless left ventricular dysfunction after myocardial infarction. *Lancet* i, 255–259.
- [113] Sharpe, N., Smith, H., Murphy, J., Greaves, S., Hart, H., Gamble, G., 1991. Early prevention of left ventricular dysfunction after myocardial infarction with angiotensin-converting-enzyme inhibition. *Lancet* 337, 872–876.
- [114] Pfeffer, M.A., Braunwald, E., Moye', L.A., Basta, L., Brown, E.J. Jr., Cuddy, T.E., Davis, B.R., Geltman, E.M., Goldman, S., Flaker, G.C., Klein, M., Lamas, G.A., Packer, M., Rouleau, J., Rouleau, J.L., Rutherford, J., Wertheimer, J.H., Hawkins, C.M., 1992. Effect of captopril on mortality and morbidity in patients with left ventricular dysfunction after myocardial infarction. *N. Engl. J. Med*. 327, 669–677, on behalf of the SAVE Investigators.
- [115] ACE Inhibitor Myocardial Infarction Collaborative Group, 1998. Indications for ACE inhibitors in the early treatment of acute myocardial infarction. Systematic overview of individual data from 100,000 patients in randomized trials. *Circulation* 97, 2202–2212.

- [116] Lewis, E.J., Hunsicker, L.G., Bain, R.P., Rohde, R.P., 1993. The effect of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibition on diabetic nephropathy. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 329, 1456–1462.
- [117] Rigat, B., Hubert, C., Alhenc-Gelas, F., Cambien, F., Corvol, P., Soubrier, F., 1990. An insertion/deletion polymorphism in the angiotensin I-converting enzyme gene accounting for half the variance of serum enzyme levels. *J. Clin. Invest.* 86, 1343–1346.
- [118] Rigat, B., Hubert, C., Corvol, P., Soubrier, F., 1992. PCR detection of the insertion/deletion polymorphism of the human angiotensin converting enzyme gene DCPI₁-dipeptidyl carboxypeptidase I. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 20, 1433–1433.
- [119] Jeunemaitre, X., Soubrier, F., Kotelevtsev, Y.V., Lifton, R.P., Williams, C.S., Charru, A., Hunt, S.C., Hopkins, P.N., Williams, R.R., Lalouel, J.M., Corvol, P., 1992. Molecular basis of human hypertension: role of angiotensinogen. *Cell* 71, 169–180.
- [120] Bonnardeaux, A., Davies, E., Jeunemaitre, X., Fe'ry, I., Charru, A., Clauser, E., Tiret, L., Cambien, F., Corvol, P., Soubrier, F., 1994. Angiotensin II type-1 receptor gene polymorphisms in human essential hypertension. *Hypertension* 24, 63–69.
- [121] Staessen, J.A., Wang, J.G., Ginocchio, G., Petrov, V., Saavedra, A.P., Soubrier, F., Vlietinck, R., Fagard, R., 1997b. The deletion/insertion polymorphism of the converting-enzyme and cardiovascular-renal risk. *J. Hypertens.* 15, 1579–1592.
- [122] Staessen, J.A., Kuznetsova, T., Wang, J.G., Emelianov, D., Vlietinck, R., Fagard, R., 1999. M235T angiotensinogen gene polymorphism and cardiovascular renal risk. *J. Hypertens.* 17, 9–17.
- [123] Villard, E., Tiret, L., Visvikis, S., Rakotovao, R., Cambien, F., Soubrier, F., 1996. Identification of new polymorphisms of the angiotensin I-converting enzyme ACE gene, and study of their relationship to plasma ACE levels by two-QTL segregation-linkage analysis. *Am. J. Hum. Genet.* 58, 1268–1278.
- [124] Ishigami, T., Umemura, S., Tamura, K., Hibi, K., Nyui, N., Kihara, M., Yabana, M., Watanabe, Y., Sumida, Y., Nagahara, T., Ochiai, H., Ishii, M., 1997. Essential hypertension and 5X upstream core promoter region of human angiotensinogen gene. *Hypertension* 30, 1325–1330.
- [125] Sato, N., Katsuya, T., Rakugi, H., Takami, S., Nakata, Y., Miki, T., Higaki, J., Ogihara, T., 1997. Association of variants in critical core promoter element of angiotensinogen gene with increased risk of essential hypertension in Japanese. *Hypertension Part 1* 30, 321–325.
- [126] Inoue, I., Nakajima, T., Williams, C.S., Quackenbush, J., Puryear, R., Powers, M., Cheng, T., Ludwig, E.H., Sharma, A.M., Hata, A., Jeunemaitre, X., Lalouel, J.M., 1997. A nucleotide substitution in the promoter of human angiotensinogen is associated with essential hypertension and affects basal transcription in vitro. *J. Clin. Invest.* 99, 1786–1797.
- [127] Poirier, O., Georges, J.L., Ricard, S., Arvelier, D., Ruidavets, J.B., Luc, G., Evans, A., Cambien, F., Tiret, L., 1998. New polymorphisms of the angiotensin II type 1 receptor gene and their associations with myocardial infarction and essential hypertension: the ECTIM study. *J. Hypertens.* 16, 1443–1447.
- [128] Cambien, F., Poirier, O., Lecerf, L., Evans, A., Cambou, J.P., Arveiler, D., Luc, G., Bard, J.M., Bara, L., Ricard, S., Tiret, L., Amouyel, P., Alhenc-Gelas, F., Soubrier, F., 1992. Deletion polymorphism in the gene for angiotensin-converting enzyme is a potent risk factor for myocardial infarction. *Nature* 359, 641–644.
- [129] Nakai, K., Itoh, C., Miura, Y., Hotta, K., Musha, T., Itoh, T., Miyakawa, T., Iwasaki, R., Hiramori, K., 1994. Deletion polymorphism of the angiotensin I-converting enzyme gene is associated with serum ACE concentration and increased risk for CAD in Japanese. *Circulation* 90, 2199–2202.
- [130] Beohar, N., Damaraju, S., Prather, A., Yu, Q.T., Raizner, A.E., Kleiman, N.S., Marian, R.R., 1995. Angiotensin converting enzyme genotype DD is a risk factor for coronary heart disease. *J. Invest. Med.* 43, 275–280.
- [131] Markus, H.S., Barley, J., Lunt, R., Bland, J.M., Jeffery, S., Carter, N.D., Brown, M.M., 1995. Angiotensin-converting enzyme gene deletion polymorphism. A new risk factor for lacunar stroke but not carotid atheroma. *Stroke* 26, 1329–1333.
- [132] Kario, K., Kanai, N., Saito, K., Nago, N., Takefumi, M., Shimada, K., 1996. Ischemic stroke and the gene for angiotensin-converting enzyme in Japanese hypertensives. *Circulation* 93, 1630–1633.
- [133] Ohishi, M., Fujii, K., Minamino, T., Higaki, J., Kamitani, A., Rakugi, H., Zhao, Y., Mikami, H., Miki, T., Ogihara, T., 1993. A potent genetic risk factor for restenosis. *Nat. Genet.* 5, 324–325.
- [134] Tiret, L., Kee, F., Poirier, O., Nicaud, V., Lecerf, L., Evans, A., Cambou, J.P., Arveiler, D., Luc, G., Amouyel, P., Cambien, F., 1993. Deletion polymorphism in angiotensin-converting enzyme gene associated with parental history of myocardial infarction. *Lancet* 341, 991–992.
- [135] Badenhop, R.F., Wang, X.L., Wilcken, D.E.L., 1995. Angiotensin-converting enzyme genotype in children and coronary events in their grandparents. *Circulation* 91, 1655–1658.
- [136] Katsuya, T., Koike, G., Yee, T.W., Sharpe, N., Jackson, R., Norton, R., Horiuchi, M., Pratt, R.E., Dzau, V.J., MacMahon, S., 1995. Association of angiotensinogen gene T235 variant with increased risk of coronary heart disease. *Lancet* 345, 1600–1603.
- [137] Katsuya, T., Koike, G., Horiuchi, M., Yee, T., Dzau, V.J., MacMahon, S., 1996. T235 variant in angiotensinogen gene is also a risk factor for coronary heart disease. *J. Hypertens.* 14_Suppl. 1, S13.
- [138] Ishigami, T., Umemura, S., Iwamoto, T., Tamura, K., Hibi, K., Yamaguchi, S., Nyuui, N., Kimura, K., Miyazaki, M., Ishii, M., 1995. Molecular variant of angiotensinogen gene is associated with coronary atherosclerosis. *Circulation* 91, 951–954.
- [139] Kamitani, A., Rakugi, H., Higaki, J., Ohishi, M., Shi, S.J., Takami, S., Nakata, Y., Higashino, Y., Fujii, K., Mikami, H., Miki, T., Ogihara, T., 1995. Enhanced predictability of myocardial infarction in Japanese by combined genotype analysis. *Hypertension* 25, 950–953.
- [140] McLaughlin, K.J., Jagger, C., Small, M., Jardine, A.G., 1995. Effect of angiotensinogen gene T235 variant on the development of diabetic complications in type II diabetes mellitus. *Lancet* 346, 1160–1160.
- [141] Tiret, L., Bonnardeaux, A., Poirier, O., Ricard, S., Marques-Vidal, P., Evans, A., Arveiler, D., Luc, G., Kee, F., Ducimetie' re, P., Soubrier, F., Cambien, F., 1994. Synergistic effects of angiotensin-converting enzyme and angiotensin-II type 1 receptor gene polymorphisms on risk of myocardial infarction. *Lancet* 344, 910–913.
- [142] Alvarez, R., Reguero, J.R., Batalla, A., Iglesias-Cubero, G., Cortina, A., Alvarez, V., Coto, E., 1998. Angiotensin-converting enzyme and angiotensin II receptor 1 polymorphisms: association with early coronary disease. *Cardiovasc. Res.* 40, 375–379.
- [143] Fatini, C., Abbate, R., Pepe, G., Battaglini, B., Gensini, F., Ruggiano, G., Gensini, G.F., Guazzelli, R., 2000. Searching for a better assessment of the individual coronary risk profile. The role of angiotensin-converting enzyme, angiotensin II type 1 receptor and angiotensinogen polymorphisms. *Eur. Heart J.* 21, 633–638.
- [144] Kiechl S, Lorenz E, Reindl M, Wiedermann CJ, Oberhollenzer F, Bonora E, Willeit J, Schwartz DA. Toll-like receptor 4 polymorphisms and atherogenesis. *N Engl J Med.* 2002;347:185–192.
- [145] Rauramaa R, Vaisanen SB, Luong LA, Schmidt-Trucksass A, Penttila IM, Bouchard C, Toyry J, Humphries SE. Stromelysin-1 and interleukin-6 gene promoter polymorphisms are determinants of asymptomatic carotid artery atherosclerosis. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol.* 2000;20:2657–2662.
- [146] Rundek T, Elkind MS, Pittman J, Boden-Albala B, Martin S, Humphries SE, Juo SH, Sacco RL. Carotid intima-media thickness is associated with allelic variants of stromelysin-1, interleukin-6, and hepatic lipase genes: the Northern Manhattan Prospective Cohort Study. *Stroke.* 2002; 33:1420–1423.
- [147] Chapman CM, Beilby JP, Humphries SE, Palmer LJ, Thompson PL, Hung J. Association of an allelic variant of interleukin-6 with subclinical carotid atherosclerosis in an Australian community population. *Eur Heart J.* 2003;24:1494–1499.
- [148] Jerrard-Dunne P, Sitzer M, Risley P, Steckel DA, Buehler A, von Kegler S, Markus HS. Interleukin-6 promoter polymorphism modulates the effects of heavy alcohol consumption on early carotid artery atherosclerosis: the Carotid Atherosclerosis Progression Study (CAPS). *Stroke.* 2003;34:402–407.
- [149] Hegele RA, Ban MR, Anderson CM, Spence JD. Infection-susceptibility alleles of mannose-binding lectin are associated with increased carotid plaque area. *J Investig Med.* 2000;48:198–202.
- [150] Risley P, Jerrard-Dunne P, Sitzer M, Buchler A, von Kegler S, Markus HS. Promoter polymorphism in the endotoxin receptor (CD14) is associated with increased carotid atherosclerosis only in smokers: the Carotid Atherosclerosis Progression Study (CAPS). *Stroke.* 2003;34: 600–604.
- [151] Worrall BB, Azhar S, Nyquist PA, Ackerman RH, Hamm TL, DeGraba TJ. Interleukin-1 receptor antagonist gene polymorphisms in carotid atherosclerosis. *Stroke.* 2003;34:790–793.

- [152]Dwyer JH, Allayee H, Dwyer KM, Fan J, Wu H, Mar R, Lusic AJ, Mehrabian M. Arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase promoter genotype, dietary arachidonic acid, and atherosclerosis. *N Engl J Med.* 2004;350:29–37.
- [153]Pallaud C, Sass C, Zannad F, Siest G, Visvikis S. APOC3, CETP, fibrinogen, and MTHFR are genetic determinants of carotid intima-media thickness in healthy men (the Stanislas cohort). *Clin Genet.* 2001;59:316–324.
- [154]Fox CS, Larson MG, Corey D, Feng D, Lindpaintner K, Polak JF, Wolf PA, D'Agostino RB, Tofler GH, O'Donnell CJ. Absence of association between polymorphisms in the hemostatic factor pathway genes and carotid intimal medial thickness: the Framingham Heart Study. *Stroke.* 2004;1935:e65–e67.
- [155]Gnasso A, Motti C, Irace C, Carallo C, Liberatoscioli L, Bernardini S, Massoud R, Mattioli PL, Federici G, Cortese C. Genetic variation in human stromelysin gene promoter and common carotid geometry in healthy male subjects. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol.* 2000;20: 1600–1605.
- [156]Rauramaa R, Vaisanen SB, Luong LA, Schmidt-Trucksass A, Penttila IM, Bouchard C, Toyry J, Humphries SE. Stromelysin-1 and interleukin-6 gene promoter polymorphisms are determinants of asymptomatic carotid artery atherosclerosis. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol.* 2000;20:2657–2662.
- [157]Ghilardi G, Biondi ML, DeMonti M, Turri O, Guagnellini E, Scorza R. Matrix metalloproteinase-1 and matrix metalloproteinase-3 gene promoter polymorphisms are associated with carotid artery stenosis. *Stroke.* 2002;33:2408–2412.
- [158]Rundek T, Elkind MS, Pittman J, Boden-Albala B, Martin S, Humphries SE, Juo SH, Sacco RL. Carotid intima-media thickness is associated with allelic variants of stromelysin-1, interleukin-6, and hepatic lipase genes: the Northern Manhattan Prospective Cohort Study. *Stroke.* 2002; 33:1420–1423.
- [159]Garg UC, Arnett DK, Folsom AR, Province MA, Williams RR, Eckfeldt JH. Lack of association between platelet glycoprotein IIb/IIIa receptor P1A polymorphism and coronary artery disease or carotid intima-media thickness. *Thromb Res.* 1998;99:85–89.
- [160]Maeno T, Koyama H, Tahara H, Komatsu M, Emoto M, Shoji T, Inaba M, Miki T, Okuno Y, Nishizawa Y. The 807T allele in alpha2 integrin is protective against atherosclerotic arterial wall thickening and the occurrence of plaque in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes.* 2002; 51:1523–1528.
- [161]de Waart FG, Kok FJ, Smilde TJ, Hijmans A, Wollersheim H, Stalenhoef AF. Effect of glutathione S-transferase M1 genotype on progression of atherosclerosis in lifelong male smokers. *Atherosclerosis.* 2001;158:227–231.
- [162]Hayaishi-Okano R, Yamasaki Y, Kajimoto Y, Sakamoto K, Ohtoshi K, Katakami N, Kawamori D, Miyatsuka T, Hatazaki M, Hazama Y, Hori M. Association of NAD(P)H oxidase p22 phox gene variation with advanced carotid atherosclerosis in Japanese type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care.* 2003;26:458–463.
- [163]Kakko S, Paivansalo M, Koistinen P, Kesaniemi YA, Kinnula VL, Savolainen MJ. The signal sequence polymorphism of the MnSOD gene is associated with the degree of carotid atherosclerosis. *Atherosclerosis.* 2003;168:147–152.
- [164]Garg UC, Arnett DK, Evans G, Eckfeldt JH. No association between factor V Leiden mutation and coronary heart disease or carotid intima media thickness: the NHLBI Family Heart Study. *Thromb Res.* 1998; 89:289–293.
- [165]Ghaddar HM, Folsom AR, Aleksic N, Hearne LB, Chambless LE, Morrissey JH, Wu KK. Correlation of factor VIIa values with factor VII gene polymorphism, fasting and postprandial triglyceride levels, and subclinical carotid atherosclerosis. *Circulation.* 1998;98:2815–2821.
- [166]Fox CS, Larson MG, Corey D, Feng D, Lindpaintner K, Polak JF, Wolf PA, D'Agostino RB, Tofler GH, O'Donnell CJ. Absence of association between polymorphisms in the hemostatic factor pathway genes and carotid intimal medial thickness: the Framingham Heart Study. *Stroke.* 2004;1935:e65–e67.
- [167]Li YH, Chen CH, Yeh PS, Lin HJ, Chang BI, Lin JC, Guo HR, Wu HL, Shi GY, Lai ML, Chen JH. Functional mutation in the promoter region of thrombomodulin gene in relation to carotid atherosclerosis. *Atherosclerosis.* 2001;154:713–719.
- [168]Willeit J, Kiechl S, Weimer T, Mair A, Santer P, Wiedermann CJ, Roemisch J, Marburg I polymorphism of factor VII-activating protease: a prominent risk predictor of carotid stenosis. *Circulation.* 2003;107: 667–670.